

DIAGNOSIS AND CORRECTION OF ATTENTION IN
ADOLESCENTS

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Annotation: This article provides information about the types and characteristics of attention, the opinions of scientists about the development of attention in adolescents, the methods of diagnosing attention and methods of its correction. These data can be effectively used for diagnosis and correction of attention in adolescents.

Key words: Attention, diagnosis, correction, teenagers, development of attention, exercise.

Attention is a necessary condition for the optimal functioning of a person's cognitive activity and occupies one of the central places in the educational and pedagogical process. The quality and success of perceiving, mastering and understanding learning material depends on the development and organization of attention.

Attention is a special feature of the human psyche. It does not exist independently - outside of thinking, perception, memory, action[1]. You can't just be attentive - you can only be attentive with something. That is why attention is called the selective direction of the mind to perform a certain task. There are different forms of attention.

Attention is the focus and concentration of mental activity on a specific object. Attention is a dynamic aspect of all cognitive processes.

You can specify several types of attention: voluntary, involuntary and post-voluntary. Involuntary attention appears directly under the influence of external

stimuli that act at the moment and cause optimal excitation in certain areas of the cerebral cortex.

Such attention does not require a person to be ready for a certain perception or action in advance. It comes on suddenly and usually doesn't last long. Voluntary attention requires conscious voluntary actions and is characterized by purposefulness, organization and stability. Voluntary attention depends on a number of main reasons:

- 1) understanding of duty and obligation;
- 2) existence of interests, motives;
- 3) work, the habit of performing this or that activity.

Post-voluntary attention occurs when the need for voluntary action to maintain voluntary attention is lost and the effectiveness of cognitive processes is preserved. This usually happens when a person is passionate about an activity.

Attention is characterized by a number of properties: volume, concentration, stability, migration, and divisibility. The amount of attention is estimated by the number of objects or their elements that can be perceived simultaneously with the same clarity and accuracy. Concentration of attention is the level of focus on an object. Stability of attention is determined by the duration of focusing on the object. Deliberate shifting of attention from one object to another describes attention shifting. Focusing attention on several objects or performing several actions at the same time characterizes the property of divided attention.

Attention is a psychological phenomenon, about which there is still no agreement among psychologists. Some consider attention to be a cognitive mental process. Others associate attention with human will and activity, based on the fact that any activity, including cognitive activity, cannot be performed without attention, and attention itself requires the manifestation of certain voluntary efforts.

The relevance of the topic is that complaints about lack of attention and determination among schoolchildren make up 90% of all complaints of parents and teachers. School psychologists and teachers are most concerned with the problem

of attention deficit disorder, perhaps because the symptoms of attention deficit disorder are the most obvious, and there are many methods for diagnosing and, most importantly, correcting such disorders.

Psychology can describe the process of attention with six main approaches. Each of them considers an aspect of human mental activity as a complex basis. But no hypothesis has been clearly recognized.

The first approach to the emotional understanding of attention was promoted by T. Ribault, who believed that attention and emotion come from each other. According to T. Ribo, the intensity and duration of voluntary attention is determined by the nature of emotions that arise through the object of attention. Such an approach to attention is considered more correct, because emotion is the possibility of satisfying the immediate need of the organism's reaction, and the organism's attention is primarily focused on such objects.

The second approach to attention was put forward by scientist I. Gebert and U. Hamilton. An image with greater intensity pushes the image with less intensity to the subconscious, and naturally only the images that remain in the mind attract our attention.

According to the third approach, attention is the result of apperception, that is, the life experience of an individual. In this case, the information received by the nervous system will be cleared by the person's need for knowledge.

The fourth approach of attention was developed by the Georgian scientist D.N. Uznadze, according to him, ustanovka expresses attention from the inside. Under the influence of Ustanovka, D. Uznadze called the process of separating a specific object from many other objects in the environment as "objectification".

The fifth approach focuses mainly on the action aspect of attention. The fact is that the orienting reflex based on involuntary attention shows the orientation of the organism to a new stimulus source and the adjustment of the analyzers to it. These processes take place with the active participation of muscles, so attention

can be called an organized method of dynamic adaptation to the environment. [2.b, 111-112.]

Unlike memory, the regulatory function of attention is more clearly manifested, which provides a basis for classifying its types according to the levels of mental regulation.

All characteristics of attention (volume, stability, etc.) develop during adolescence, especially the ability to focus on something for a long time. If necessary, teenagers can change their focus without much effort. But at the same time, the division of attention and restlessness also appear due to some reasons.

The following methods can be used to diagnose attention in adolescents:

1. Burdon's "Correction Test" methodology (the methodology determines the stability of attention, shift and speed of task completion),
2. "Schulte table" method (to determine the speed of attention shift, division and sensorimotor reaction),
3. Sisoev and Marishuk's modification of Schulte's table (studying the shift and division of attention according to Schulte's table),
4. Methodology for determining the scope of attention (the scope of the student's attention is determined)
5. Munsterberg test (for attention concentration and selection)
6. (Lineogram test (attention shift, mental motor functions, plasticity of mental functions),
7. Red-black table (modification) (distribution of attention),
8. Counting and calculating according to Kraepelin (determining complex sensory-motor reactions, work ability, stability of voluntary attention, speed of mental processes), etc.

One of the main forms of human cognitive activity are sensations that attract attention and force them to focus on something or an action. Sensations are mental processes that arise from the direct impact of the objects and events of the surrounding reality on the sense organs. From a cognitive point of view, the

leading role among all analyzers belongs to vision and hearing, although it is believed that stimuli of vital and social importance are reflected more often and more through hearing than through vision[3].

The full development of mental processes, including all types of sensations, largely depends on certain conditions, among which attention is of particular importance[4].

The most important parameters for working on the development of attention are concentration and stability.

Work on the development of attention is carried out in two directions:

1. Using special exercises that teach the main features of attention.
2. Using exercises in which mindfulness is formed as a property of a person.

Often, parents complain about the instability of attention, accuse the teenager of apathy and laziness. They are actually wrong. If a person does not have passion for work, his attention will definitely be distracted. One of the characteristics of educational work in secondary school is the need to frequently shift students' attention from one content to another. Mathematics lesson is replaced by history, then physics, biology. Such frequent and sudden changes in attention are a big deal for people with an inert type of nervous system. At the same time, it should be remembered that the quality of attention is affected not only by educational conditions, but also by age characteristics. Thus, the physiological changes observed at the age of 13-15 are accompanied by increased fatigue and irritability, and in some cases lead to a decrease in attention characteristics.

It is estimated that about 70% of normal children who are considered healthy and attend public schools have attention deficit disorder. This can be for a variety of reasons, including medical reasons.

We offer some methods of "Shamatha" meditation, used by ancient Buddhists and Tibetan yogis and scientifically proven by Dr. Alan Wallace, as the most effective method for developing attention.

"Shamatha" meditation

Correct posture for meditation

Body position - sitting, for comfort you can use a pillow or a bench in meditation. If your joints hurt, you can sit on a chair or a hard chair.

The back is flat. Do not bend or bend your back. We feel how the body is stretched from the top of the head to the tailbone.

We do not lower our head and do not throw it back, the position of the head is as if looking at a point on the floor 3-4 meters away from us.

Shoulders and arms are relaxed, stomach is not tense.

The hands are placed palm to palm and the hips are supported.

Eyes closed or half closed - comfortable.

It is allowed to change the position of the legs with closed eyes.

We begin each meditation with a gradual relaxation of the facial muscles. We focus on: forehead, eyebrow ridges, between the eyebrows (it is important to free this area), cheekbones, cheeks, upper lip, lower lip, chin. Then we move our attention throughout the body, releasing excess tension.

During meditation, we make sure that the muscles are not too tense, and at the same time we check the presence of a "thread" from the top of the head to the . We try not to move, for beginners it is allowed to change the position of the legs with closed eyes.

From time to time we focus on the area between the eyebrows and release this area[5].

"Shamatha for breathing" technique

The best meditation technique for relaxation is to observe your breath.

This is especially true in the evening, when a hectic day is behind us, when the mind is full of thoughts, and there is a noise in the head. Most of the time you are also emotionally overwhelmed, maybe even angry.

You still have to sit to meditate. But first, relax by observing your breath.

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Get ready, sit in a chosen position or on a pillow. Take a few minutes to meditate. Take a few deep breaths through your nose and exhale through your mouth. Then we breathe naturally and only through the nose.

After that, focus all your attention on the breathing process and start counting the inhalations and exhalations.

You can do it, we "take one breath" (we breathe in), "one breath out" (we breathe out), "we take two breaths, two breaths out" and so on. We will do this until ten. This is the first cycle. Do this for a few cycles.

Breathing is our natural rhythmic process that connects us to something very deep, mysterious, truly real and eternal. It is the thin thread that holds us together in this life. Maybe that's why breathing is so interesting to us.

Breathing is also comfortable because it is not static, thus keeping us awake and not causing us to fall asleep.

In the process of counting, the mind becomes calmer, more stable and less distracted. By focusing on your breathing, you will go deeper into meditation.

After counting the breath, focus on the point where the air enters our body - this is the tip of the nose, the nostrils, and focus on the sensation when it touches the air.

Meditation on the object.

After performing the breathing technique, you can move on to meditation on the object. But you can continue meditating on the breath and end there.

It is recommended to imagine the object in front of you at arm's length, the size of a finger (even if it is very large live) at the level of the eyebrows.

Look at the image, then close your eyes and remember it. If this is a person, imagine him alive. Hold this image for 3-5 minutes. That's enough.

If you notice how the color of the image of the object has changed, for example, the shape or other qualities, restore the image to its original properties[6].

"Hand meditation" technique

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This meditation technique is good for beginners. Thanks to the large number of sensitive receptors, we can feel our palms very well.

Before meditating, take an upright, comfortable position. The palms can be placed inside each other, they can lie on the knees apart from each other. With your breath, focus on all parts of the body, feel their relaxation and fullness. Try to capture a sense of inner peace and tranquility. Focus all your attention on the palms, pay attention to the signals received from them. Without being distracted by thoughts or other feelings, try to feel them as fully as possible and relax the body in general. At some point, vibration, pulsation may appear. When your attention fills your hands, they seem to increase in size. The usual perception of the body can also change - the distance from the head to the palms seems smaller than usual.

This meditation technique can be used in any situation - on the way to work, on public transport or while walking. Time - 10-30 minutes a day.

"Point meditation" technique

The modern way of life (active surfing on the Internet, abuse of social networks, etc.) causes a person's attention to become superficial and windy in a short time. Most of us are used to short articles and notes (preferably with pictures) and it's hard to stay focused while reading a long book, for example.

"Lowness" in the head often interferes with sleep and even causes headaches.

Ancient spiritual and modern psychological practices offer many different techniques for developing focus, quieting the mind, and stopping internal chatter.

One of the most effective of these practices is the "point concentration" technique. This technique is very simple and as old as the whole world.

Concentration on one point

Develops concentration (accuracy and retention).

Calms the mind, eliminates internal dialogue or monologue (who has what)

Develops the will

Acts on self-expression and tricks of the mind

Practice

We start by drawing a black dot the size of a match head on the paper.

We hang our creation on the wall so that the point is at eye level.

We sit comfortably on the floor, bench, pillow or chair - the main thing is that the back is straight. It is necessary to sit at a distance of 50-70 cm from the wall.

We set the timer for a certain time (30/40 minutes).

We practice: we achieve constant attention and focus all our attention on this point. When thoughts come, let them pass—don't cling to them or dwell on them. If the attention is distracted somewhere, we gently bring it back to the point.

We do not pay attention to optical "gluki" - this is not an effect of practice.

The image may be blurred. Even when we stop seeing, we continue to focus on this point.

And don't forget to smile internally while doing this and other exercises[5]!

Attention is the direction and concentration of consciousness, which increases the level of emotional, intellectual or motor activity of a person. If attention becomes extremely unstable, then a person cannot concentrate on a cognitive task. Violation of attention stability is one of the causes of poor learning, which leads to impaired memory and the ability to think objectively. At the same time, the function of executing behavioral programs is also affected. There is disordered behavior.

Voluntary attention reaches a high level of development during adolescence. Adolescents can already engage in a certain type of activity for a long time. Nevertheless, at this age, you can often hear complaints from parents and teachers about carelessness and laziness. The main reason for this problem is the lack of enthusiasm for work, which affects the entire cognitive sphere of the teenager. In this regard, it is recommended to use exercises that develop attention for teenagers. In particular, some methods of "Shamatha" meditation can be used.

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